

A Review of Preclinical Blast Models for Real-World Relevance in Traumatic Brain Injury Research

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Abstract

Traumatic brain injury (TBI) has emerged as a critical concern in modern warfare, with blast-induced TBI being particularly prevalent among military personnel. This high prevalence has led to significant research investment aimed at understanding the cause, treatments, identification biomarkers and prevention strategies for the injury. Many studies are preclinical in nature that require accessible and repeatable blast models. However, developing a model to accurately reflect the complexities of real-world explosive environments encountered during military training and operations within a laboratory setting is challenging, resulting in the creation of numerous designs. This paper evaluates the strengths and limitations of blast models, including open field and shock tubes, used for preclinical blast analysis and how they scale to human injuries. By understanding the specific effects of open field blasts and integrating this knowledge with clinical observations, researchers aim to enhance the development of protective measures and therapeutic interventions for TBI. These findings emphasize the importance of replicating real-world scenarios in preclinical research to improve the translation of laboratory results to practical applications in military and civilian applications.

Introduction

Traumatic brain injury (TBI) is a critical focus in military research, driven by increased recognition of exposure to blasts during training and combat operations¹⁻⁴. While studies involving weapon systems and explosive blasts have increased, standardized guidance for investigating blast-induced traumatic brain injury (bTBI) is limited, contributing to variability in findings and raising concerns about the complexity and often poorly understood nature of this condition⁵⁻⁸. The overarching goals of blast research are to clarify the mechanisms of injury, guide the design of protective equipment, develop effective medical treatments, and ultimately reduce the risk of injury in military and civilian populations. Unlike other forms of TBI such as blunt force trauma, bTBI results from the interaction of shock waves with the head, transmitting energy into the brain. This energy transfer can cause shearing of nerve fibers (diffuse axonal injury)⁹⁻¹², vascular damage that affects blood flow^{1,10,13,14}, impaired mitochondria and synapses and their dysfunctions¹⁵⁻¹⁹. In addition to neuronal damage, the mechanical forces can stimulate mechanosensitive glial cells, triggering neuroinflammatory responses that contribute to both acute and chronic pathology^{1,16}.

Research into bTBI encompasses a broad array of topics, ranging from the initial cause of the injury to its diagnosis, potential biomarkers, and treatment options^{16,20-22}. Preclinical studies have utilized mammalian and non-mammalian models such as worms²³, mice^{9,13,17-19,24-33}, rats³⁴⁻⁶¹, goats⁶², sheep⁶³, and pigs⁶⁴⁻⁶⁸, to simulate different aspects of brain injury. These models have been instrumental in elucidating the underlying mechanisms of TBI, identifying potential biomarkers, and testing therapeutic interventions^{7,8,20,38}. Computational (in silico) models have been used to simulate shock wave propagation and tissue-level responses⁶⁹⁻⁷¹, enabling the study of mechanisms such as cavitation that are difficult to capture experimentally. Preclinical testing remains essential for informing and validating these computational models, ensuring biological relevance. Translating findings from animal models to human clinical applications remains a challenge⁷² scaling models based on total body mass, brain mass, or head size are not always accurate^{73,74}. Further research is needed to refine these models and improve their translational relevance, thereby enhancing the applicability of preclinical findings to clinical practice.

Critical gaps remain in our understanding of bTBI, particularly regarding long-term effects and how brain tissue responds to shock wave energy^{75,76}. Data analysis is often limited to peak pressure measurements, complicating comparison across studies and the development of standardized treatment protocols⁷⁷. Shock wave characteristics such as duration, rise time, and impulse should be measured and evaluated to better understand the mechanism of injury and inform potential treatments or preventive strategies. Initiative such as PRECISE-TBI⁷⁸ and ODC-TBI⁷⁹ are establishing consistent testing protocols and standardized data sharing practices which promotes collaboration and enhances reproducibility. Adoption of unified reporting standards and comprehensive data-sharing frameworks will enable more reliable comparisons and accelerate progress towards developing effective interventions.

The importance of studying bTBI extends beyond preclinical or academic investigation, as the knowledge gained from these studies directly informs efforts to improve the safety and care of military personnel. By understanding the specific effects of blast exposure, researchers can contribute to better protective measures^{80,81}, more effective medical treatments⁵⁷, and the development of protocols aimed at reducing the risk of TBI such as limiting the number of rounds fired per day in training or increasing standoff distances from explosives⁸². The Long-Term Impact of Military-Relevant Brain Injury Consortium-Chronic Effects of Neurotrauma Consortium (LIMBIC-CENC) clinical program, which investigates TBI in military personnel, has concentrated primarily on injuries from controlled and uncontrolled detonations^{83,84}. Yet, its assessment to date lacks specific focus on blast-related injuries, with only one blast-related question being asked of warfighters⁸⁵. This highlights the need for more comprehensive clinical evaluations that capture the full complexities of blast events.

The current literature on TBI models presents a fragmented picture, with a wide range of models and techniques that vary significantly in design and application^{16,86–88}. The lack of standardized methodologies hinders the ability to draw consistent conclusions and limits the development of universally applicable clinical practices. Many existing bTBI review articles fail to address open field blast testing or provide sufficient detail about how shock tube models relate to real world environments^{16,86–88}. This review examines the strengths, repeatability, and ecological validity of various models in replicating the types of blast exposure experienced by military service members. Studying bTBI is crucial for addressing a significant and urgent issue facing military personnel, therefore, the development and use of models that are repeatable and relevant to real-world scenarios are vital to ensuring the safety of current and future warfighters.

Main Section

Blast Phenomenon

In the study of bTBI, understanding the overpressure phenomenon is essential. A shock wave is defined as a pressure wave travelling faster than the speed of sound in the medium of travel, decaying at a rate that is dependent on the density of the medium^{89–92}. In most bTBI studies, this medium is air, but how the shock wave is generated can differ^{17,26,77,86}. A blast wave is a specific type of shock wave produced by a high explosive and is characterized by a distinct positive and negative phase. Figure 1 illustrates a simplified blast wave featuring a sharp, nearly instantaneous pressure spike, followed by an exponential decay, and a subsequent negative phase before returning to ambient pressure^{21,93}. Detailed descriptions of the key blast wave parameters such as peak pressure, rise time, duration, and impulse are provided in the following paragraphs.

Figure 1: Simplified blast wave labeled with measurable characteristics

Simplified Waveform

The Friedlander waveform models an idealized blast wave that occurs in open air, free of obstacles and reflections^{94,95}. This model is commonly used in experimental and theoretical studies because it provides a straightforward framework for analyzing key wave characteristics like peak pressure, rise time, duration, and impulse⁹⁶⁻⁹⁸. Despite its simplicity, the Friedlander waveform often serves as a baseline for comparison with more complex waveforms observed in real-world scenarios, yet it does not capture the additional complexities introduced by reflections, structures, or confinement, as discussed in the next section.

Complex Waveforms

In real-world scenarios, blast waves often deviate significantly from the idealized Friedlander form. These deviations arise from interactions with surfaces, obstacles, and other environmental factors. For charges that are elevated above the ground or near a surface, a Mach stem can form as the incident wave reflects. The reflected wave merges with the original wave at a single point known as the triple point. Below the triple point is the Mach stem which travels outward with higher pressure than the incident wave. Figure 2 illustrates the formation of a Mach stem as the blast wave reflects off the ground and merges with the incident wave. Reflection waves also form when the blast wave encounters a wall, vehicle or other surface, often resulting in multiple reflections.

Figure 2: Formation of a Mach stem from an elevated charge

Mach stems and other wave interactions can result in pressures far exceeding those predicted by the Friedlander model ^{99,100}, creating challenges for accurately modeling and mitigating blast effects. In confined spaces, such as urban environments, additional complexities arise, including wave focusing where waves converge at specific points. Multiple waves converging can prolong the duration and increase the magnitude of the blast wave.

Wave Characteristics

Peak pressure refers to the maximum pressure exerted on the target during the blast event. This pressure can be categorized into two types seen in Figure 33: side-on pressure and head-on pressure. Side-on pressure, sometimes called incident pressure and can be representative of static pressure, is measured perpendicular to the blast wave's direction, while head-on pressure, also called reflected pressure, is measured at the surface facing the blast wave front, where it is significantly higher due to the wave's reflection and amplification. The level of reflection is dependent on surface area of the sensor mount, so should be designed to be a similar size to the target of interest ⁹⁹. The distinction between these two pressures is important for accurately assessing the force imparted to different parts of the body or test subject material.

Figure 3: A: Head-on pressure measurement B: side on pressure measurement

Rise time refers to the period required for the pressure to increase from ambient levels to its peak. A shorter rise time corresponds to a more abrupt application of force ^{101,102}. The rapidity of this pressure increase is a critical factor in determining the nature and severity of the resulting damage, as it affects how quickly energy is transferred to the target. Figure 1 depicts the rise time as an almost instantaneous rise to peak pressure, which is a common feature of many blast waves.

Duration is the time span over which the pressure acts on the target. Both the magnitude and the positive and negative phase duration can influence the target's response. Duration is also related to injury severity as the longer the duration of the shock wave the more severe the injury ¹⁰³.

When studying blast waves, one of the key characteristics that is often overlooked is the decay rate. The decay rate refers to how quickly the pressure drops after reaching its peak, and it plays a role in determining the overall effect of the blast wave ^{104,105}. Understanding the decay rate is essential for accurately modeling real-world blast conditions, especially when using laboratory tools like shock tubes and advanced blast simulators (ABS). The rate at which the pressure decays is influenced by factors including the medium through which the wave is traveling (water, air, solid materials) ¹⁰⁶⁻¹⁰⁹ and confinement (shock tubes or open air) ⁹⁰. In denser mediums such as water, the decay rate is slower ^{110,111}, while in less dense media such as air, the wave can dissipate its energy faster ⁹⁰. When a blast wave is confined such as in a shock tube, the pressure does not drop off as quickly because it has a smaller volume for expansion and decay ^{112,113}.

Traditionally, blast wave studies have primarily reported only the positive phase, the sharp rise in pressure following an explosion, while often neglecting the subsequent negative phase. As the blast wave dissipates, pressure drops below atmospheric levels, creating a suction effect that pulls air and debris back toward the blast origin ¹¹⁴. This effect has been shown to increase debris velocity and contribute to structural collapse, particularly in buildings already weakened during the positive phase ¹¹⁵⁻¹¹⁷. At the cellular level, the rapid pressure shifts between the positive and negative phases generate shear stress and mechanical strain, which can damage cell membranes, disrupt normal signaling pathways, and impair structural integrity ^{71,118,119}. In brain tissue, such pressure fluctuations have been linked with spreading depression, abnormal hemodynamic responses, neuroinflammation and oxidative stress all of which contribute to blast-induced neuronal dysfunction ¹²⁰. Additionally, computational models suggest that blast wave transmission and rapid head motion produce diffuse injury patterns, further demonstrating how pressure oscillations affect biological structures ⁷¹. Despite these consequences, shock tube experiments and preclinical studies rarely account for the negative phase, as most shock tube designs prioritize generating repeatable positive pressure pulses, often suppressing or distorting the negative phase. A more complete understanding of blast dynamics requires consideration of both phases, particularly when modeling real-world explosions and their impact on structures, materials and biological systems.

Impulse refers to the pressure exerted by the blast wave over a specific duration ¹²¹, shown in green in Figure 1. It is most often quantified as the positive phase impulse, calculated by integrating the area under the pressure-time curve during the positive phase of the blast. This metric reflects the

total energy transferred to the target. Impulse is a critical factor in assessing the damage potential of a blast, as it accounts for both the magnitude and duration of the applied pressure^{99,112,122}. The negative phase impulse, calculated by integrating the area under the curve during the negative phase (when the pressure falls below atmospheric levels) can also be significant. This phase contributes additional dynamic forces on the target, such as suction effects that pull air and debris back toward the blast origin. Including both positive and negative phase impulses provides a more comprehensive assessment of the total energy and potential damage associated with the blast wave.

The key wave characteristics of the blast wave—peak pressure, impulse, duration, decay rate, and rise time—are fundamental to understanding blast waves dynamics and their effects on the brain. However, in practical scenarios, blast waves rarely follow this ideal form. Blast waves frequently encounter obstacles and structures, leading to reflections that alter the expected waveform²¹, and could amplify injury. Longer duration waves have been shown to increase tissue damage²¹. Accurate measurement and analysis of these parameters through experimental studies are important as idealized models alone cannot fully capture the complexity of blast exposures.

It is important to provide succinct definitions of common blast wave characteristics and test parameters frequently used in blast testing. Table 1 offers a summary of terms and measurements typically encountered in most tests and that align with parameters incorporated into the common data elements data management platform for blast models from PRECISE-TBI^{26,27}.

Table 1: Terms and definitions for exposure metrics in bTBI testing

Metric	Definition
Static Overpressure Peak	Highest recorded side-on pressure
Reflected Overpressure Peak	Highest pressured recorded with a head-on sensor
Positive Wave Duration	Time during which the target experiences positive pressure
Overpressure Rise Time	Time taken for pressure to rise from ambient to peak
Impulse	Total force exerted by the pressure wave over time
Positive Phase Impulse	Force over time for the positive pressure phase
Pressure Sensor Location	Position where pressure is measured
Animal Body Exposure Type	How the animal is oriented relative to the blast
Animal Body Angle	Specific angle of the animal’s body during exposure
Animal Restraint Method	Method used to restrain the animal during testing

Instrumentation Requirements

The introduction of piezoelectric sensors in the 1940s enabled more accurate measurement of blast wave⁸⁹. Data acquisition systems (DAS or DAQ) allow for the real-time visualization of sensor output in the field, providing instantaneous results. The sensor’s response rate, often described in terms of its rise time, determines how quickly the sensor can react to changes in pressure. Since blast waves are characterized by extremely rapid pressure fluctuations, sensors with slower response times may fail to capture the sharp rise to peak pressure or other high-frequency

components of the waveform. For blast and shock wave studies, sensors with rise times in the microseconds (μs) range are typically used^{123–125}. Ideally, the sensor respond faster than the expected rise time of the blast wave, which may range from a few microseconds to milliseconds depending on the energy and environment of the blast event¹²⁶. Common free field blast sensors have frequency response rates of 300-400 khz^{127,128}. It is also important to note that all sensors have a programmed discharge time constant (dtc)¹²⁹ and comparing duration or impulse between different sensors may not be representative. As a basic rule, the dtc needs to be longer than the event you want to measure.

Equally important is the DAS sample rate, which dictates how frequently pressure data is recorded. To accurately capture the details of a blast waveform, especially peak pressure, the sample rate must be sufficiently high. If the sample rate is too low, critical features of the waveform, such as the exact peak pressure and the rapid rise, may be missed or misrepresented. This can lead to underestimation of peak pressures, rise times, and impulse values, thereby skewing the interpretation of the shock event. The appropriate sampling rate depends on the specific characteristics of the shock wave, including its rise time and duration. Sampling rates as low as 10 kHz can capture the peak pressure and waveform shape for moderate-intensity shock waves (Mach number < 2) with durations of a few milliseconds¹³⁰. However, this sampling rate may not resolve the rapid rise time of the shock front, especially in short-duration waveforms (< 1 ms). For studies requiring precise measurements of fast transitions, such as peak overpressure, rise time, or impulse, higher sampling frequencies are essential. A minimum sample rate of 1 MHz (1 million samples per second) is recommended to ensure sufficient resolution for capturing the fast dynamics of the wave^{123–125,130–132}.

Since peak pressure is directly related to the destructive potential of the wave, failure to accurately measure this parameter could result in the underestimation of blast severity, compromising both experimental conclusions and safety assessments. When considering frequency response, it is important to ensure that the DAS system has a bandwidth equal to or greater than that of the sensor, as the sensor often becomes the limiting factor in capturing high-frequency pressure transitions. Using sensors with high response rates in conjunction with high-sample-rate DAS systems ensures the integrity of these pressure measurements and helps prevent underreporting or omission of important aspects in the blast wave profile.

Preclinical Models for bTBI

Animal models play an important role in the study of TBI, providing understanding of the mechanisms of injury, potential biomarkers, and therapeutic interventions. Species including worms, mice, rats, goats, ferrets, sheep, and pigs, have been used in these models, each offering unique advantages and limitations. Despite the diversity of models, one common limitation is the lack of standardized data analysis beyond the basic parameter of peak pressure, which hinders

comprehensive cross-study comparisons. The vast difference in preclinical models and exposure levels are not always applicable to the injury type being studied. Other review articles^{8,16,21,87,88} have in depth analysis and discussion on models such as fluid percussion injury (FPI), controlled cortical impact (CCI), weight drop injury, penetrating ballistic-like brain injury (PBBi), closed head impact, and projectile concussive impact (PCI) but review articles related to shock tube or open field blast models are limited^{16,73,133}.

Injury Metrics and Outcomes in TBI studies

The complexity of bTBI and the different laboratory methods of reproducing the injury make it challenging to draw definitive conclusions, leading to a wide variety of study focuses with no universally accepted answers. Due to the varied outcomes studied, it is imperative that the model used to induce injury is both consistent and relevant to real-world conditions.

Traumatic brain injury is broadly classified into impact and non-impact injuries. Impact injuries involve a direct blow to the head, such as those seen in sports, flying debris, or vehicular accidents, while non-impact injuries include blast-induced TBI (bTBI) and other forms of trauma that do not result from direct contact. The Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS)¹³⁴ is commonly used in clinical settings to assess the severity of TBI in humans, providing a rapid evaluation of a patient's level of consciousness based on verbal, motor, and eye-opening responses.

Advanced imaging techniques, such as magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and computed tomography (CT), are used to visualize structural and functional brain changes^{135–138}. These techniques have been instrumental in identifying diffuse axonal injury (DAI), tau pathology^{139,140}, and other hallmarks of TBI, yet their applicability to bTBI remains an area of active investigation.

At the cellular level, calcium dysregulation¹⁴¹, mitochondrial dysfunction¹⁷, neuroinflammation and oxidative stress⁴⁶, are leading secondary injury mechanisms that are reported to contribute to neuronal damage and cell death following blast exposure.

From the physiological perspective, several system-level functional changes can develop following bTBI. Disruption of the glymphatic system¹⁶, which is responsible for clearing metabolic waste from the brain, may also exacerbate long-term deficits. Behavioral and functional assessments in animal models, including cognitive measures (e.g., Morris water maze, novel object recognition), sensorimotor evaluations (e.g., rotarod, grip strength), anxiety and sociability assessments (elevated plus and open field tests)^{16,73}, provide insight into behavioral changes that occur following blast exposure at both acute and chronic stages of the injury. Additionally, biomarkers such as neuron-specific enolase (NSE), myelin basic protein (MBP), neurofilament light-chain (NfL) S100B, ubiquitin carboxyl-terminal hydrolase L1 (UCH-L1), and glial fibrillary acidic protein (GFAP) have been explored for their diagnostic potential in assessing brain injury^{21,22,73}.

Despite extensive research, the field of TBI remains fragmented, with studies differing in injury models, exposure parameters and frequency, durations, and outcome measures. The lack of integration of those factors has led to inconsistent findings and hindered the development of standardized diagnostic and treatment protocols. A more comprehensive approach that combines clinical data with advanced imaging, biomarker analysis, and detailed behavioral assessments is needed to fully understand the complexities of TBI and to develop effective interventions.

Open Field Blast Models

Open field blast models detonate high explosive charges in the open air and allow the resultant blast wave to propagate freely and dissipate based on the natural surroundings. Controllable variables are the type of charge, mass of the charge, height of the charge and distance to the target. The local elevation and weather conditions are uncontrollable variables but can affect the peak pressure and decay rate.

Table 2 shows key metrics specific to open field blast testing. These metrics, such as explosive type, mass, and height are critical for characterizing blast exposure and ensuring comparability across studies. Environmental factors, including atmospheric pressure, humidity, and weather conditions, should also be documented, as they can affect shock wave propagation and pressure decay. Additionally, variables like shock wave velocity and animal positioning relative to the blast source are essential for accurately assessing the forces experienced during an open field blast. Consistently reporting these metrics in studies would improve reproducibility and facilitate more meaningful comparisons between experiments.

Table 2: Terms and definitions for exposure metrics in bTBI testing specific to open field blasts

Metric	Definition
Species	Animal type used in the test
Explosive Type	Type of explosive used in the test
Explosive Mass	Amount of explosive used
Animal Distance	Distance between the animal and the explosive
Explosive Height	Height at which the explosive is detonated
Animal Height	Height of the animal above ground level
Atmospheric Pressure	Ambient air pressure at the test site
Humidity	Moisture level in the air
Weather Conditions	General environmental conditions at the time of the test
Weather Temperature	Air temperature at the time of testing
Shock Wave Velocity	Speed at which the blast wave propagates

A charge placed on the ground will have a hemispherical blast wave expansion but is often not used as craters are created in the ground, making a repeatable model not possible. When a charge is elevated the shock wave propagates radially outward in all directions from the charge until it

reaches a free surface, such as the ground, causing a reflected wave¹⁴²⁻¹⁴⁴. Repeatability in blast studies refers not only to reproducing the physical characteristics of the blast (pressure, duration, impulse, reflections) but also to achieving consistent biological outcomes, such as similar injury severity scores or biomarker responses in test subjects. While exact replication of every injury parameter may be impossible, controlling the blast conditions to produce reliable measurable physiological or behavioral impairments is important for comparing results across experiments and evaluating protective measures or interventions. The initial, unimpeded wave is called the incident shock wave. When the incident and reflected shock wave combine at the interface, a third wave known as the Mach Stem forms. The intersection between these three waves is known as the “triple point”^{145,146}. When using spherical surface air bursts for TBI testing, test subjects can be placed so the triple point occurs before the subject, allowing only one shock wave to impact the test subject or after the triple point, allowing for multiple reflections.

The Kingery-Bulmash (KB) equations can be used to estimate pressure from hemispherical surface bursts^{91,105}. For spherical air bursts, the applicability of KB equations is more limited, and their predictions should be used cautiously, as they do not fully account for the effects of height or reflections¹⁴⁷. Blast wave propagation can differ slightly depending on the charge height, as the blast wave propagates radially outward in all directions from the charge, causing reflections off the ground¹⁴²⁻¹⁴⁴. Elevated charges will have similar peak pressure and rise time to charges placed directly on the ground, of the same mass and distance from the target, but positive phase duration and impulse can vary depending on the magnitude of the reflection present in the wave profile and exposure. The incident and reflected wave can be seen in Figure 4 where there are 2 peaks, as opposed to Figure 1. The timing and magnitude of the reflections change with the height of the charge, height of the target, and the distance between. Figure 4 shows example pressure profiles from the Department of Veterans Affairs Open-Field Blast Core (OFBC) model¹⁴⁸. Figure 4A shows the side-on pressure measured as the blast wave passes by a sensor, while Figure 4B is the head-on pressure measured as the blast wave hits the sensor and reflects back.

Figure 4: Pressure profile from the Missouri S&T Open-Field Blast Core model¹⁴⁸ A: side-on pressure from two pencil probes B: head-on pressure from a flush mount sensor

Open field blast models mimic real world blast waveforms as the overpressure decays naturally in the surrounding and allows for negative overpressure. The flexibility of the open field setup allows researchers to adjust variables such as charge height, target positioning, and explosive type to recreate a variety of blast conditions, ranging from simple to complex waveforms. This flexibility makes open field models ideal for studying the wide range of injuries resulting from blast exposure.

In summary, open-field blast models closely mimic real-life blast conditions with decay rates and negative phases representative of high explosives detonated in free air. Open field charges create an incident shock wave, but depending on the height of the charge, also result in ground reflections. These ground reflections can be beneficial as they combine with the incident wave to form a Mach Stem if a simple waveform is desired or multiple reflective surfaces can be implemented to add complexity to the exposure. The lack of control over environmental variables, such as wind and humidity, could introduce variability in the results but at close distances with a high velocity blast wave, differences are negligible. Ground reflections from the open field charges can provide additional impacts to the target resulting in increased impulse. Fully understanding how to alter the triple point and shock reflections is important when designing within this setup as the resultant waveform can range from a simple waveform to a more complex weapon system depending on the charge and target placement.

Table 3 presents data from TBI studies that utilized open field blast models. These data were collected through searches of Scopus (RRID:SCR 022559) and PubMed (RRID:SCR 004846) using the search terms of “open field blast”, “open field blast tbi”, “tbi animal models”, “animal explosive tbi”. The studies are grouped by laboratory as each research group generally used the same model. Metrics included in the table are the species, body orientation, explosive type, distance from the charge and peak pressure. While pressure alone is not an ideal metric to compare to clinical outcomes it remains the most commonly used reported parameter. At the time of publication, it is still not standard to report other shock wave characteristics such as rise time, impulse and duration, which are often absent. The model catalog tool that was developed and is maintained as part of PRECISE-TBI (RRID:SCR 022252) serves as a database for locating relevant publications and associated metrics across TBI models, supporting in the reproducibility of preclinical TBI research with standardized protocols¹⁴⁹. Although fewer studies have utilized open field methods compared to shock tube or other testing approaches, commonalities in study designs are evident, particularly in the types of blast setups and animal orientations used. For example, many studies oriented animals in the prone position and use the explosive Composition C4 (C4). The distances from the blast source varied widely, ranging from as close as 0.002 meters to 7 meters. Despite this variability, reported peak pressures in open field tests generally range from 17.2 kPa and 409.2 kPa. Notably, two of five laboratories did not report peak pressure values from their experiments. In contrast, shock tube studies have reported peak pressures ranging from 30 kPa to 1723.7 kPa. The variety of animal models used, including mice, rats, swine, and pigs,

reflects efforts to explore species-specific responses. However, rather than indicating a standardized approach, this variability underscores the challenge of achieving consistency across studies. Differences in body orientation, species physiology, and exposure conditions further complicate direct comparisons. These factors should be carefully considered when evaluating the applicability of open field blast data to broader field of TBI research.

Table 3: Open field blast data from 5 different experimental models

Research Group/University	Species used	Animal body orientations	Explosive Type	Distance from blast (m)	Peak Pressure (kPa)	Paper
Tel-Aviv University, Israel	ICR mice	Prone	TNT	4 to 7	17.2 to 37.9	^{24,25}
Missouri University of Science and Technology and VA (Open-Field Blast Core)	C57BL/6J mice and Sprague Dawley rats	Prone and upright	C4	2.15, 3, 4, 7	42.9 to 82	^{13,17–19,26–28,139}
Northwest Institute of Nuclear Technology, Xi'an, China	Sprague-Dawley rats	prone	PETN	0.002	Not reported	³⁵
Wayne State University	Yucatan swine	prone	C4	3.1 to 3.6	148.8 to 409.2	^{67,150}
Defense Research Establishment, Stockholm, Sweden	Swedish country strain pigs	prone	Composition B	4	Not reported	⁶⁶

Shock Tube Blast Models

Shock tubes have historically been widely used in blast research due to their ability to generate consistent shock waves using high-pressure gas or small amounts of explosives. These systems offer controlled environments for studying blast wave effects, including the formation of shock waves, reflections, and vortex rings. Explosively driven shock tubes require significantly less explosive mass than open-air testing while still producing a strong incident shock wave ⁶¹.

Shock tubes can vary widely in geometry, including tube length, diameter, shape, and end configuration (open, closed, baffled). Nevertheless, each individual setup can produce controlled and repeatable waveforms when operated under consistent conditions ^{61,151–153}. In non-explosively driven shock tubes, key wave characteristics are influenced by the type of driver gas (e.g., air,

helium) and the properties of the burst membrane (material, thickness) ^{96,154}. The shock waves generated in these confined system often lacks a significant negative phase due to the continued pressurization from the expanding driver gas and the geometry of the tube ¹⁵⁵.

While shock tubes offer a controlled and repeatable environment for studying blast effects, several key exposure metrics must be reported to ensure consistency across studies. Table 4 outlines essential parameters specific to shock tube models while Figure 5 shows a standard shock tube. Factors such as tube length, diameter, and shape influence shock wave formation and propagation ¹⁵⁶, while the driver gas type and membrane material determine the characteristics of the pressure wave ^{96,154}. The end configuration of the tube (e.g., open or closed) can significantly impact wave reflections and secondary loading conditions on test subjects ¹⁵⁷. Burst membranes play a crucial role in shock tube operation, controlling the timing and strength of the shock wave. Common materials include Mylar, aluminum, or plastic films, with thickness adjusted to achieve a specific rupture pressure. Thicker membranes require higher driver pressures, producing stronger shock waves ¹⁵⁸. Rupture occurs when internal pressure exceeds the membrane's tensile strength, often at pre-scored points, but the break is not always clean and fragments can be ejected into the driven section ¹⁵⁹. These debris pieces may strike test subjects or interfere with sensor data collection. Despite their importance, membrane properties and debris mitigation strategies are often underreported, making comparisons across studies more difficult. Additionally, accurate documentation of the animal location within the tube is crucial, as small variations in positioning can lead to substantial differences in pressure exposure. Standardizing the reporting of these parameters would enhance the comparability of shock tube studies and improve the ability to relate findings to real-world blast exposures.

Table 4: Terms and definitions for exposure metrics in bTBI testing specific to shock tube models

Metric	Definition
Blast Total Number	Number of blasts conducted in a test series
Driver Gas Type	Type of gas used to drive the shock wave
Area Value	Cross-sectional area of the blast tube
End Configuration Type	The way the end of the tube is configured (open, closed, etc.)
Animal Location	Position of the animal inside the shock tube
Membrane Material Type	Type of material used for the burst membrane
Membrane Thickness	Thickness of the burst membrane
Tube length	the length of the driven section of the shock tube
Tube diameter	the internal diameter of the driven section of the shock tube
Tube shape	the geometric shape of the driven section of the shock tube

In preclinical research, animals have been placed in four primary locations relative to the shock tube shown in Figure 5: location 1, inside the tube (whether open or closed), at the end of a closed tube (location 2), directly outside a tube (location 3), and at some distance outside an open tube (location 4) ^{112,160}. Inside the tube, the blast wave is typically planar with higher peak pressures

and minimal negative phase due to the confinement and continued pressure from the expanding gas ¹⁵⁵. Reflections from the tube walls result in complex internal wave interactions that can produce multiple pressure peaks during the positive phase ⁹⁰. At the tube exit, the wave transitions from planar to radially expanding, and a vortex ring forms due to shear forces and flow separation ¹⁶¹⁻¹⁶⁴. This ring moves downstream and can deliver additional pressure and impulse to the target. As the distance from the tube exit increases, the target experiences both the expanding shock wave and the advancing vortex ring. The resulting waveform can include prolonged pressure tails and secondary peaks due to vortex-ring impacts and reflected shock interactions ¹⁶⁵⁻¹⁶⁷. The presence and strength of these effects depend on the geometry of the tube and the test subject's distance and size.

Targets that occupy more than 10% of the shock tube cross-sectional area can experience increased dynamic pressure due to flow constriction and resulting lift and drag forces ^{112,168}. Larger diameter tubes are recommended in such cases to minimize distortion of the intended waveform. Unlike shock tubes, open-field blasts are not subject to this spatial constraint and typically produce waveforms with more pronounced negative phases.

Figure 5: Target locations in shock tube testing ¹⁶⁹

While traditional shock tubes often produce waveforms that deviate from free-field Friedlander shapes, particularly due to the absence of a substantial negative phase, advancements in tube design have aimed to address this limitation. For example, increasing the driver length or pressure can increase decay time and impulse, helping to approximate open-field blast characteristics ^{146,157}. Systems such as the Advanced Blast Simulator (ABS) incorporate features such as wedge-shaped drivers ^{113,170-172} and end-wave eliminators ^{170,173}, which facilitate the formation of a negative phase. While these advancements and improved the ability to generate idealized Friedlander waveforms in a laboratory setting, challenges remain when attempting to replicate complex waveforms produced in real-world explosions involving surface interactions, multiple reflections, and Mach stem formation. Most modern systems are therefore designed to mimic simplified free-field waveforms, with improvements enabling better approximation of free-field conditions but not fully replicating their complexity.

Despite advances in shock tube technology and characterization, interpreting results from blast-induced TBI studies remains difficult due to confounding factors such as wall reflections, vortex ring effects, and variations in geometry. Differences in driver gases, diaphragm materials, animal orientation, and placement further contribute to variability in exposure profiles and biological outcomes, complicating cross-study comparisons. To evaluate current practices, peer-reviewed publications were identified through Google Scholar (RRID:SCR 008878) and PubMed using search terms such as “shock tube,” “blast-induced TBI,” and “animal model.” Studies were included if they involved experimental shock tube exposures and reported relevant setup information. Table 5 summarizes findings from 20 research groups, highlighting the range of methodologies. Rodents, particularly male Sprague-Dawley rats, were used in 90% of laboratories, while a smaller number used larger species such as pigs, rabbits, or rhesus monkeys. It is important to note that rodents are lissencephalic, meaning their cortices are smooth, whereas larger species have gyrencephalic, or folded, cortices. These anatomical differences could influence how blast waves propagate through the brain, potentially affecting shear stress or patterns of injury. Findings from rodent models may not fully replicate the biomechanical effects observed in species with folded cortices, showing the need to consider brain structure when interpreting preclinical results. Most animals were positioned prone, with 60% of studies placing them inside the shock tube to expose subjects to a more planar waveform. About 35% placed animals outside the tube to simulate free-field conditions, although 15% did not report the animal’s location at all.

Circle cross-section tunnel designs were the most common (50%), while 35% of studies did not specify tunnel shape. Compressed air or gas was the most frequently used driver medium (45%), followed by helium (25%). Peak overpressures ranged from 30 kPa to over 1700 kPa, with 15% of laboratories failing to report peak pressure values. Although shock tubes can replicate a wide range of blast intensities, many exposures reported in the literature exceed thresholds relevant to typical military or occupational settings. For example, the U.S. military designates 28 kPa (4 psi)¹⁷⁴ as a limit for repeated exposure, above which the risk of eardrum rupture and mild TBI increases. Pressures exceeding 100 kPa (14.5 psi) are commonly associated with a risk of pulmonary injury in unprotected individuals^{1,168}; however, actual injury risk in combat scenarios depends on numerous factors, including body orientation, exposure duration, and the use of personal protective equipment (PPE), which can significantly mitigate effects. As such, real-world injury thresholds remain an area of active investigation.

While peak pressure is often the sole reported metric, duration, rise time, and impulse are equally critical to understanding the mechanical loading experienced by tissues. These parameters shape the energy transferred to biological systems and strongly influence injury pathways. Their omission in most reports limits the ability to assess physiological relevance and hinders meaningful comparison across laboratories. Without standardized exposure metrics and more comprehensive documentation, reproducibility and translational value remain limited.

Table 5: Shock tube and advanced blast simulator data from 20 different experimental models

Lab/Shock Tube	Animals used	Animal body orientations	Driver gas	Tunnel shape	Animal location	Peak Pressure (kPa)	Paper
University of Kentucky, McMillan blast device	Sprague-Dawley Rats	Prone	Compressed air or oxyhydrogen	Cylinder	Inside the expansion chamber	100 to 200	¹⁷⁵
Walter Reed Army Institute of Research	Sprague-Dawley Rats, Long Evans Hooded rats, ferrets	Prone	Compressed air	Square and circular	Inside the tube	36 to 142.2	^{34,36,51–60,176,177}
Johns Hopkins University Applied Physics Laboratory	C. elegans, wistar rats, C57BL/6 mice, rabbits	prone	Helium	Cylinder	Inside and outside the tube	252.3 to 338.9	^{23,29,50,178}
University of Iowa	WldS mice	prone	Compressed air	Cylinder	Inside the chamber	Null	⁹
University of Wisconsin	Sprague-Dawley rats	prone	Helium	Circular	Outside the tube	100 to 450	^{47–49}
Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University	C57/BL6 mice, Sprague-Dawley rats, Yucatan and Göttingen minipigs	Prone	Helium, or oxygen and acetylene	Rectangular	Inside the tube	68.95 to 525	^{44–46,179–181}
University of Oklahoma	Sprague-Dawley rats	Supine	Nitrogen	Null	Outside the tube	551.6	^{43,182}
Baylor or BYU	Sprague-Dawley rats	Prone	Compressed air	Null	Inside the tube	74	⁴²
Wayne State University	Sprague-Dawley rats	prone	helium	Null	Inside the tube	96.5 to 153	^{41,136}
Third Military	C57BL/6 mice	Null	Null	Null	Null	321.2	^{30,183}

Medical University, Chongqing, China							
West Virginia University	Sprague-Dawley rats	prone	Nitrogen	Null	Outside the tube	Null	40
University of Gothenburg, Gothenburg, Sweden	Wistar rats, pigs	Prone	Null	circular	Inside the tube	30-60	39,65,184
New Jersey Institute of Technology	Sprague-Dawley rats, 129S1/Sv1 mJ, A/J, C57BL/6J, NOD/ShiLt J, NZO/HILtJ, PWK/PhJ, WSB/EiJ Mice	Prone	Compressed gas	Square	Inside the tube	60 to 420	185,186
University of Pennsylvania	C57BL/6 mice	Prone	Helium	Circular	Outside the tube	120 to 500	31,32
Shanxi Medical University, Taiyuan, Shanxi Province, China	Long Evans rats	Prone	Air	Circular	Outside the gun	0 to 206.8	37
University of California, Los Angeles	Sprague-Dawley rats, C57BL/6 mice	prone	Air	Circular	Inside the chamber	163.9 to 1723.7	187
Lovelace Foundation for Medical Education and Research Albuquerque, New Mexico	Rhesus monkeys, dogs, goats, rats, guinea pigs	Null	air	cylinder	Inside the chamber	206 to 344	188,189

Duke University	Yorkshire pigs	prone	Compressed gas	circular	Outside the tube	107 to 500	68
ARA mobile shock tube	Yorkshire and Yukatan pigs	Null	Compressed gas	Null	Null	379	64,190
Boston University/Fraunhofer Center for Manufacturing Innovation	C57BL/6 mice	prone	Compressed gas	Null	Null	Null	33

Scaling Methods

Preclinical research on TBI is primarily aimed at understanding the underlying mechanisms, identifying biomarkers for diagnosis and prognosis, and improving therapeutic strategies. One of the most significant challenges in this field is the translation of findings from preclinical models to clinical outcomes. The anatomical and physiological differences between species necessitate careful consideration when designing experiments and interpreting results^{74,191–194}. Scaling methodologies, such as mass scaling, brain scaling, and head scaling, provide frameworks for this translation process, ensuring that experimental data from animal models are relevant to human conditions.

Mass scaling is a widely used approach that involves adjusting experimental parameters according to the entire body mass of the subject^{72,192}. This methodology is based on the premise that physiological responses to TBI scale proportionally with the organism's body mass¹⁹³. By normalizing data across species of varying sizes, researchers can better predict human responses based on animal model data. However, mass scaling can oversimplify complex biological responses, potentially neglecting species-specific anatomical and physiological differences. For instance, the distribution of brain tissue and the structural integrity of the skull can vary significantly between species, affecting the outcome of mass-scale experiments. While mass scaling provides a starting point, its inability to address these anatomical variations limits its applicability for predicting human outcomes.

Brain scaling specifically accounts for the mass of the brain, offering a more focused approach than mass scaling^{72,192}. The mass and structure of the brain can significantly influence the biomechanical and physiological responses to TBI. By concentrating on brain-specific properties, brain scaling provides a more accurate representation of neurological responses, especially concerning the impact of traumatic forces. Nevertheless, this method may not account for other critical anatomical differences, such as variations in skull thickness or cerebral vascular

architecture, which can also affect the transmission of forces and subsequent injury patterns requiring a more comprehensive scaling model to ensure relevance to human models.

Head scaling, often referred to as Jean's model ⁷², incorporates the size, shape, and structural characteristics of the head, including skull thickness and brain volume. Head structure can significantly influence the transmission and impact of blast waves, particularly in blast injuries ^{192,194}. Jean's model is thus highly relevant for studying bTBI, where the unique characteristics of the head play a crucial role in determining injury severity and outcomes ⁷². While head scaling provides a detailed and accurate representation of head-specific factors, it requires comprehensive anatomical data, which may not always be readily available. Moreover, implementing this method can be complex, demanding sophisticated computational models and precise measurements.

Scaling methodologies are essential for translating preclinical research findings into clinical outcomes. Each method has its strengths and limitations, and the choice of scaling approach should be tailored to the specific research question and the nature of the TBI model used. For example, while mass scaling provides a broad comparison across species, brain scaling offers a more targeted analysis of neurological outcomes, and head scaling is particularly suited for studying the biomechanical aspects of blast injuries.

Conclusion

High explosives exhibit unique characteristics when detonated in the open air, including a fast rise time, exponential decay as the blast wave freely expands to the surroundings and a distinct negative phase. Environmental objects such as walls, vehicles, buildings, or people impede the flow of the blast front, resulting in multiple pressure spikes and prolonged durations. Accurately mimicking these dynamics in a laboratory setting for preclinical evaluation has proven challenging and comparisons between research groups are often difficult.

Open-field testing captures interactions with terrain and ground reflections, closely mimicking real-world scenarios, but such testing is not always practical or feasible. Shock tubes and Advanced Blast Simulators offer controlled environments for studying shock waves, allowing for precise adjustments to parameters such as peak pressure and impulse. However, the confined nature of these devices alters wave propagation, often resulting in extended decay times compared to open-air detonations. Variations in tube geometry further impacts rise times and return to ambient pressure, making direct comparisons across different setups or with open-field models impractical. Adjustments to parameters such as driver gas type, membrane thickness, tube length, and end configuration can improve alignment with specific blast characteristics. However, differences in decay rate and waveform evolution should be carefully considered when interpreting results.

Among the 25 preclinical blast models reviewed, 20 used shock tubes or simulators and 5 used open-field explosive testing. Rodents were the dominant species overall, with 84% (21/25) of studies using mice or rats, and rats used in 64% (16/25) of models. Reporting of exposure metrics

varied considerably. Peak pressure was unreported in 20% (5/25) of all studies, specifically, 3 of the 20 shock tube models and 2 of the 5 open-field studies. Where provided, shock tube peak pressures ranged from 30 kPa to over 1700 kPa, while open-field exposures spanned 17.2 kPa to 409.2 kPa. However, even when peak pressure was reported, few studies included other essential waveform characteristics such as rise time, duration, or impulse, which are critical for understanding injury mechanisms and replicating real-world blast scenarios. The absence of standard metrics and terminology across these studies continues to hinder reproducibility and complicates comparisons between models. Ongoing efforts by groups such as PRECISE-TBI, aim to address these gaps by developing standardized metrics and common data elements. Making these resources publicly available will further facilitate consistent methodology and improve cross-laboratory comparisons. As the field moves toward greater translational relevance, future work must prioritize full waveform characterization and transparent reporting of exposure conditions. Establishing consensus protocols, particularly around exposure metrics like rise time, impulse, and decay, will be essential for aligning preclinical studies with operational blast realities and improving the reliability and clinical translation of experimental bTBI models.

Transparency, Rigor, and Reproducibility Statement

The review was not preregistered because it falls under the category of a traditional literature review that employed a systematic search strategy but did not implement full systematic review methodology or quantitative meta-analysis. A comprehensive literature search was conducted using PubMed, Web of Science, and Google Scholar to identify peer-reviewed studies describing pre-clinical blast models, including explosive-based, gas-driven, and wire-driven approaches. Search terms included combinations of “blast,” “TBI,” “shock tube,” “explosive model,” “gas-driven blast,” “overpressure,” and “pre-clinical.” Additional relevant publications were identified through reference chaining from review articles. As this review involved only publicly available literature and did not include individual patient data, institutional review board approval was not required.

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Author contribution (after acknowledgements)

R.L.B.: Conceptualization, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, writing—original draft, review and editing. P.J.V.: Conceptualization, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, writing review and editing. C.E.J.: Conceptualization, formal analysis, funding acquisition, investigation, methodology, project administration, resources, supervision, writing review and editing

Statements and declarations

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Data availability

All data used throughout the manuscript is provided in the paper.

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